



(a) Level of education.



(b) State.



(c) Nature of the organization.



(d) Experience.



(e) Work area.

Figure 1: Participant profile: demographic data.



(a) You have researched or worked with laws beforehand.



(b) You currently research or work with laws.



(c) Level of experience with law.

Figure 2: Participant profile: experience with data protection laws.



Figure 3: Usability evaluation according to the participants.



Figure 4: Evaluation of ease of use according to the participants.